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ABSTRACT

Introduction: This study aims to examine family medicine publications in Turkey using three widely utilized databases in the medical literature (Karakullukçu & Ardiç, 2023).

Materials and Methods: Data were collected on March 10, 2025, from the "Web of Science," "Scopus," and "PubMed" databases, which are commonly used in medical research. The search was conducted using the terms "*family medicine*" AND ("*Turkey*" OR "*Türkiye*") without any restrictions on date or document type, targeting the title, abstract, and keyword fields. The data were analyzed using the bibliometrix package and the Biblioshiny application developed by Aria and Cuccurullo (2017: 959) for the R programming language (Kocak, 2014).

Results: In the relevant field within Turkey, 646 records were identified in WoS, 238 in Scopus, and 127 in PubMed. After removing duplicates, 756 unique publications across 417 journals were found. The earliest publication appeared in 1989, and the number of publications gradually increased, peaking in 2021 with 66 publications (8.7%). The top three journals by publication count were the *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*, *European Journal of General Practice*, and *Konuralp Medical Journal*. The leading universities in terms of contributing authors were Istanbul University (11.2%), Hacettepe University (8.7%), and Ankara University (7.7%). A total of 5,759 keywords appeared across the 756 articles. The most frequently used keywords were "Turkey" (96; 1.7%), "human" (77; 1.3%), and "female" (75; 1.3%). The term "family medicine," which was the focal point of this study, ranked eighth (62; 1.1%). These publications have been cited a total of 11,217 times. The countries citing these works most frequently were Turkey (9,381; 83.6%), the USA (407; 3.6%), and the UK (323; 2.9%). Thematic analysis showed that research in family medicine mainly centers around "prevalence," referring to the distribution of diseases and their links to family medicine services. In contrast, areas like traditional medicine have emerged as more niche topics.

Conclusion: Bibliometric analyses provide a comprehensive overview of research in the field (Sutcu, Tabassi, Sencar, & Memon, 2013). Evaluating the current landscape through such analyses is crucial for shaping future research directions.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Turkey, family medicine, bibliometric analysis

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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